

Integrative Approaches in Species Sensitivity Distribution Modeling Cross Species Modelling

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Abstract

Species Sensitivity Distributions (SSDs) are widely used to characterize ecological and toxicological hazard thresholds, yet their robustness is often limited by uneven taxonomic data coverage and variability in experimental information. This study investigates the use of molecular descriptors to develop SSDs that can generalize across taxa while incorporating Applicability Domain (AD) assessment to evaluate model reliability. The workflow includes data harmonization, descriptor selection, SSD construction, and AD-based filtering to ensure transparent and interpretable predictions. This approach aims to enhance the consistency and biological relevance of SSDs and extend their applicability to data-poor species, supporting more reliable and comprehensive chemical hazard assessment.